

How Data Visualization Enhances Data Science

Data visualization is the process of presenting data in a graphical or visual format, such as charts, graphs, maps, or images. Data visualization can help data scientists and other stakeholders to explore, analyze, communicate, and understand data in an effective and efficient way. In this article, we will discuss how data visualization enhances data science in four aspects: data exploration, data analysis, data communication, and data storytelling.

Data Exploration

Data exploration is the first step of any data science project, where data scientists try to get familiar with the data, identify its characteristics, and discover potential patterns or anomalies. Data visualization can facilitate data exploration by providing a quick and intuitive overview of the data, revealing its distribution, trends, outliers, and correlations. For example, a histogram can show the frequency of different values in a variable, a scatter plot can show the relationship between two variables, and a heatmap can show the intensity of values in a matrix. Data visualization can also help data scientists to compare different subsets of data, such as different groups, categories, or time periods, by using techniques such as faceting, stacking, or clustering. Data visualization can also enable data scientists to interact with the data, such as filtering, zooming, or selecting, to focus on specific aspects or details of the data.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the core of any data science project, where data scientists apply various methods and techniques, such as statistics, machine learning, or deep learning, to extract insights, knowledge, or predictions from the data. Data visualization can enhance data analysis by helping data scientists to understand the results, evaluate the performance, and validate the assumptions of their methods and techniques. For example, a confusion matrix can show the accuracy and errors of a classification model, a ROC curve can show the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity of a binary classifier, and a residual plot can show the deviation of the observed values from the predicted values of a regression model. Data visualization can also help data scientists to compare different methods and techniques, such as different models, algorithms, or parameters, by using techniques such as overlaying, juxtaposing, or animating. Data visualization can also enable data scientists to refine their methods and techniques, such as tuning, optimizing, or debugging, by providing feedback and guidance.

Data Communication

Data communication is the final step of any data science project, where data scientists communicate their findings, conclusions, or recommendations to their intended audience, such as clients, managers, or peers. Data visualization can improve data communication by making the data more accessible, understandable, and memorable to the audience. For example, a bar chart can show the ranking of different categories in a variable, a line chart can show the change of a variable over time, and a pie chart can show the proportion of different segments in a variable. Data visualization can also help data scientists to emphasize the key points, highlight the differences, and illustrate the relationships of their data, by using techniques such as color, size, shape, or annotation. Data visualization can also enable data scientists to engage their audience, such as asking questions, soliciting feedback, or inviting participation, by providing interactivity and functionality.

Data Storytelling

Data storytelling is the art and science of combining data, visualization, and narrative to tell a compelling and persuasive story with data. Data storytelling can enhance data science by integrating the three aspects discussed above: data exploration, data analysis, and data communication. Data storytelling can help data scientists to explore the data from different angles, analyze the data with different methods, and communicate the data with different techniques, to create a coherent and comprehensive story that answers the questions, solves the problems, or achieves the goals of the data science project. Data storytelling can also help data scientists to connect with their audience, by using techniques such as context, emotion, or humor, to create a story that is relevant, interesting, and impactful.

Conclusion

Data visualization is an essential and powerful tool for data science, as it can enhance data science in four aspects: data exploration, data analysis, data communication, and data storytelling. Data visualization can help data scientists to explore, analyze, communicate, and understand data in an effective and efficient way, and to create original and meaningful stories with data that can inform, persuade, and inspire their audience.